

High-Energy Physics and Open Science: Supporting the Engagement of High-Energy Physicists in Open-Science practices through Research Digital Libraries

Confirmation review report

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Abstract

Open Science requires actions from the researcher community and the scholarly communication community alike. Numerous reports exist on barriers influencing researchers' decision making in that regard. Among these, the perceived barrier between established workflows and the need for documentation of scientific outputs is attributed to scientists' disengagement from "Open-Science practices". This study aims to answer the question of "how to engage High-Energy Physicists with Open-Science practices via Digital Research Libraries" and build a set of practical recommendations.

The research is designed to be carried out in four phases. By investigating the context and workflows of HEP research, information needs and information practices of HEP scientists and their usage and perception of information services, this thesis will provide an analysis of Open Science practices and potential in HEP, and for the first time, propose solutions to engage HEP scientists in Open-Science practices and the role of information professionals in supporting researchers with overcoming barriers.

This report outlines the background, research questions, methodology and some preliminary results acquired during the first year of study.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

The Open Science movement calls for the public sharing of scientific knowledge in all formats. The term 'Open Science' encapsulates a wide range of open initiatives, including open access, open data, open source software, and open educational resources. (Fecher & Friesike, 2013). As a result of incorporating all information that pertains to the scientific research process, this approach generates a vast amount of content and demands new, community-driven services to organize and make content useful (Alemu, Stevens, Ross & Chandler, 2012). It is an open question how these services can be built, and tailored to specific communities, by a collaboration of the scientists, library and information professionals, and technologists (Hey & Hey, 2006).

However, previous studies on the specification and adoption of Open-Science practices have suggested that both barriers and opportunities exist. While many scientists believe making the research process more transparent by sharing their research outputs will bring positive benefits to their own careers and help to address issues such as the "reproducibility problem" in the long run (Tenopir et al., 2015), the hesitation in trusting this new, developing paradigm, and taking action accordingly is still pronounced. This sentiment is understandable, considering that introducing uncertainties to existing workflows in effect takes up already precious research time, especially in the High Energy Physics (HEP) context (Dallmeier-Tiessen et al., 2014).

With the enormous amount of scientific data and other scholarly artefacts being generated, stored, curated, used and re-used in the field, the HEP community is facing particular challenges that are well suited to exploring the potential of raising community awareness and encouraging practical involvement in the development and organization of information services. In particular, the large-scale Research Digital Library (RDL, digital libraries that cater their services to scientific researchers. The term is extensively used in the report and is specifically defined in the beginning of the literature review chapter) INSPIRE¹ at the European Organization of Nuclear Research (CERN) provides a unique opportunity to study the situation. CERN is the central hub of the global HEP community – it currently host the most powerful particle accelerator and largest detectors in the world, which enable more cutting edge research than any other HEP lab in the world. As the main, long-standing digital library platform, INSPIRE offers integrated scientific information services to the HEP community worldwide. The digital library currently

¹ INSPIRE is a collaborative digital library service operated by five HEP institutions/laboratories around the world. In addition to CERN, these are SLAC and FermiLab in the US, DESY in Germany and IHEP in China. It is the successor of SPIRES developed as far back as 1969, which grew to be the first web server outside of Europe and the first database on the Web.

holds over one million records and allows access to about 0.5 million Open Access full-texts. These artefacts are aggregated and attributed to about a hundred thousand author profiles. As the main community information aggregator, INSPIRE also strives to incorporate novel added value services to meet the HEP community's demand, such as citation extraction (for text and data publications) and analysis functions for machine generated author profiles. In face of Open Science, INSPIRE is exploring the roadmap for HEP research data catalog integration, at the moment, access to research datasets from INSPIRE record is realized through interconnection with sister data repository platform HEPData.

There is an increasing need for the INSPIRE content to be easily discoverable, retrievable and citable as favoured by Open Science advocates, in particular up-stream research objects such as data, software and their connections to publications (Rueda et al., 2013). At the moment, examples of discovery entry points are a known author or a connection from a related instance of the same scientific idea. However, this discovery is only currently enabled by high-quality description of each scientific record, as well as the establishment of a network of interconnected relationships of records. Examples of such networks are the set of all scientific artefacts (articles, preliminary reports, conference papers, thesis as well as data sets and software) attributed to an individual author, or the set of research artefacts representing a single scientific idea (from preliminary conference report to a published article, and/or a thesis or a review). Considerable amounts of resources are being put into developing and improving the scholarly communication infrastructures that enable the interoperability of these networks, such as Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) (Brown & Cruise, 2015; Fenner et al., 2014).

With the diversity of information flowing into INSPIRE from multiple sources, it is not possible to create such links through the conventional approach of depending on librarians to discover and annotate these connections. Curators either lack the capacity to address the sheer volume of the task or the deep field-specific knowledge required to identify connections in a manner that is sufficient for discoverability by field experts.

The success of science crowdsourcing initiatives² (Stodden, 2010) has given inspiration to digital research libraries to take the similar approach, but within a specific expert community, to solve the thorny challenge brought about by data-intensive, heavy-computation research. Allowing researchers themselves to share, publish, annotate, correct and discuss their output easily, even when the quantity of content and content types increase rapidly, could potentially be a new way of enabling the coherent organization of the information. The historical position of CERN and the availability of the INSPIRE digital library provide the perfect

² Citizen science projects using the efforts and ability of volunteers to help scientists and researchers deal with the flood of data that confronts them. Exemplified by the project Galaxy Zoo.

condition for a dedicated case study on the digital information services in the HEP context.

1.2 Research aim

The aim of the research is to build a set of practical recommendations for engaging high-energy physicists with Open-Science practices through RDLs. INSPIRE offers added value services like providing "claiming tools" for authors and users to identify the interconnection among authors and research outputs, or submission forms that enable the user community to address errors in the description of the material upon its ingestion. By investigating the potential of the community-engaging features³ on INSPIRE, this Ph.D. work is an opportunity to address the crucial overarching challenge for digital libraries in general. The scientific community at CERN will provide the research environment to test previous assumptions on RDLs usage and motivations for user participation and to gain further insights on opportunities and barriers that were not previously anticipated.

Synthesized from existing literature within the research scope, the full set of research questions are listed here:

Main research question: How can Research Digital Libraries support and engage HEP scientists with Open-Science practices (or "Open practices")?

Sub-research questions:

1. What are the general workflows and strategies used in the HEP research process, and what are the communication cultures, environments, and conventions in the HEP field that shape and form research practices?
2. What information is needed to conduct HEP research? What strategies are used to find the required information?
3. What Open-Science practices can be adapted to the workflows of HEP researchers?
4. What Open Science related services does INSPIRE offer currently and are these services engaging users?
5. How do Open Science services affect the way that scientists interact with the RDLs?
6. What potential opportunities exist for RDLs in supporting HEP research activities?

³ "A feature is a distinguishing characteristic of a software item (e.g. performance, portability, or functionality)", Standard IEEE 829

To address these research questions, the research is divided into four phases using a mixed (qualitative and quantitative) methods approach. The first phase of the study will enable an in-depth understanding of disciplinary research workflows, conventions and resulting practices, then cross-reference these practices with Open Science recommendations to determine the compatibility of "Open practice" and HEP research. The results of phase one will then provide a foundation for phase two, analysis of the INSPIRE digital library user-system interaction log (shortened as "user log" in the rest of the document), by suggesting crucial variables in user behaviour data. Results of the user log analysis will shed light on how users engage with various INSPIRE services, which will be used as a support for formulating a hypothesis on design and development of enhancements to better engage users with the system. Phase three will be a validation process of the hypothesis generated as the result of previous investigations, using qualitative focus group method to test the concept of supporting "Open practices" by guiding research habits with the RDLs. Finally, an integration and interpretation stage is proposed to consolidate all the findings and build a holistic response to the original research question, along with a discussion of necessary next steps.

It is valuable to explore the methodology proposed in this study in face of new community-driven Library and Information Science (LIS) service development at CERN, for example the Analysis Preservation framework, which comprises scientific artefacts from every stage of the research lifecycle. This newly conceived preservation service raises additional curation challenges and the collaboration between the research community and LIS service providers.

2. Literature review

The purpose of conducting this literature review is to gain comprehensive background knowledge about the research topic, identify gaps in current research activities, and draw clear boundaries for the investigation that will follow.

Open-Science practices lean heavily on the support of innovative data sharing and data management technologies, and libraries are in the pivotal position to provide the services that meet Open Science requirements (European Commission, 2012). From the RDLs perspective, an effective implementation of such service can only be achieved through close partnerships between the information professionals, technologists and the user community (Adams & Blandford, 2004). In view of this, the literature review chapter is organized into five sections, starting with (1) a brief description of literature selecting and searching method used, followed by three main subjects: (2) the RDLs and academic librarianship; (3) the term Open Science; and (4) scholarly communication and information services in the HEP community. The final section (5) presents a brief summary of the literature, and pinpoints the gaps to be explored in the next steps of this PhD project. It is worth noting that this is not yet a comprehensive literature review for the overarching PhD project. Some topics that are briefly touched on may become of more interest in later stages of research. Ongoing literature reviews will be carried out as the project progresses.

To keep the literature research within scope, definitions of key concepts are presented here.

Research Digital Library is defined as a digital library that seeks to best assist and facilitate research activities by offering content ingestion, curation, retrieval and added value services.

Open Science refers to the newly conceived scientific paradigm that promotes transparency in scientific conduct, emphasising accessibility, discoverability, interoperability, reproducibility and reusability of scientific activity processes and products.

High-Energy Physics community mainly focuses on the physics research personnel in the HEP field -- opposed to atomic/ molecule physics, condensed matter physics or astrophysics -- consisting of experimental physicists and theoretical physicists, who are the primary user group of the INSPIRE digital library, the particular disciplinary RDL that will be focused on in this PhD project.

2.1 Literature searching method

Guided by the research aim, the subject scope for the literature review is, in broad terms, academic libraries and librarianship, Open Science and scholarly

communication and services in HEP. The literature review at the first stage of the project mainly serves the purpose of surveying the landscape of relevant fields, laying down a foundation for the research, and providing clear evidence for setting precise boundaries of the scope of the PhD project.

To achieve the goal of comprehensiveness and highest relevancy, two strategies for literature searching were used in the process of identifying the literature: systematic keywords searches on online academic databases and in-person expert recommendation (with subsequent citation tracking, onwards and backwards). To keep abreast of new materials released during the research, Google Scholar alerts for "Open Science", "digital library", "crowdsourcing" and "data curation", were set up to provide daily updates. The type of literature surveyed comprised journal articles, government and funding body reports, conference papers, books, blog posts and a small number of other miscellaneous files (e.g. working group papers, service descriptions, and initiative announcements, etc.).

The research topic is the engagement of HEP scientists with Open-Science practices via RDL platforms. It is evident that relevant literature includes the broader landscape of RDL development, the Open Science movement, and scholarly communication in HEP. In parallel, literature on research methodologies was also extensively explored during the research-planning phase, but these are discussed in the methodology chapter of this report.

2.2 Research Digital library and academic librarianship

Discussion and exploration on the role of digital libraries in academic environments and the role of librarians in the digital era grow in parallel, and influence each other as the revolution of information technology takes place. As the digital library technologies mature and scholarly contents become increasingly accessible, the potential role of the librarian becomes much more multifunctional. On top of the traditional information curator role, studies also suggest that librarians take on the digital library designer role - engaging the user community to design useful and usable services (Adams & Blandford, 2002), and more recently, the best research practices facilitator role - encouraging policy compliant practices through innovative value-adding services offered by the digital library platform (Sayogo & Pardo, 2013). This section is organized along these two strands of intertwined concepts.

2.2.1 The development of RDLs

Studies on RDLs started with the emergence of available technologies, and have extended in multiple directions: From the design of RDLs, technical infrastructure, to their evaluation and value-adding services. Among these, this study is mostly interested in the research literature on design, evaluation criteria and value-adding

services. It is worth noting that institutional/ disciplinary/ electronic theses and dissertation repositories are not the foci of the project, although many times end users of digital library and digital literature repositories fail to recognize the difference between the two (meaning for example the questions "how do PubMed and PMC differ" are required on the FAQ page of the PubMed Central website⁴). The research is mostly interested in the added value service aspect of digital libraries. In the scientific research context, RDLs cater their services to the researchers' needs. These services could be unique to the discipline, or to the conventions of the specific user group. RDLs, aiming at assisting research process by facilitating scholarly communication, have the motivation, flexibility and resources to explore its potential to accommodate and develop these services.

Many researchers have attempted to formulate a general definition of digital libraries. An early vision for digital libraries is a digital representation of the physical library, or a digital content repository. The concept soon matured in the 90's, leading to new system development initiatives that emphasized both functionality and ease of use (Belkin, 1999). Now many digital libraries have become complex hubs of scholarly information databases that support various information seeking and exchange practices. To quote Candela and colleague (2011): "the 'history' of digital library is the history of a variety of different types of information systems that have been called 'digital libraries'". Pragmatically, the meaning of digital library can be sketched out from its functionalities. 20 years ago Graham (1995) listed in *Requirements for the Digital Research Library* basic tasks and commitments a RDL should address, including the tasks of housing digital contents and providing access infrastructure and policy, on top of organizational, institutional and fiscal commitments. These guidelines for RDL development still hold true today.

The design of RDLs has been studied using a range of different methods. Systematic evaluation of information behaviours of RDL users in different disciplinary backgrounds has identified diverse information needs and contrasting information searching and use habits. Paepcke (1996) divided researchers into "detectives" and "librarians", which in turn described two contrasting information consuming and producing habits: firstly, intuitive and impatient researchers who have low tolerance for documentation, and secondly, systematic, thorough researchers who tend to keep process logs. Another study took a disciplinary perspective based on Biglan's (1973) typology of disciplinary subject matter characteristics on undergraduates' information seeking behaviours, which showed that students' approach to information seeking varied by the hard/soft, pure/applied and life/nonlife dimensions of their research subject (Whitmire, 2002). Hemminger and colleagues' survey with academics (2007) revealed changes in information seeking behaviours due to increasing availability of digital resources, which lead to much higher reliance on RDLs. This result echoes another qualitative research on the same subject, in

⁴ <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/about/faq/#q2>

which the author also indicated an emerging challenge: the increased accessibility of information led to less recognition for libraries and librarians (Wang, Dervos, Zhang, & Wu, 2007).

Considerable attention was drawn to developing advanced information retrieval techniques to better accommodate direct searching through vast amounts of data (Amolochitis, Christou, Tan, & Prasad, 2013; Berry, Drmač, & Jessup, 1999; Hanani, Shapira, & Shoal, 2001; Mendonça, Cimino, Johnson, & Seol, 2001; Nagendra Prasad, Lesser, & Lander, 1996). IR plays a significant role in addressing the discoverability issue in the Open Science paradigm mentioned in the following section.

Availability of large volumes of digital content, tools and bibliographical resources provided the foundation for RDLs to offer novel services in a wide range of areas. These value adding services have always been a parallel theme of research in the field, as exemplified by Goh and Leggett (2000) who advocated that digital libraries should not stop at providing collection maintenance and retrieval services, since "the ultimate goal for any academic library is to serve the scholarly needs of its users". The inclination of "mobilizing" – the disaggregation and re-aggregation of – information in journal articles during research was investigated and provided evidence and support for potential integrated information filtering feature in RDLs (Bishop, 1999), which parallel in concept to the new CERN Analysis Preservation service that is being developed for the HEP community at CERN (Chen et al., 2016). In other disciplinary communities, researchers continue to propose alternative content for DRLs to host, including geographical, botanical information and digital video contents, illustrated the potential for RDLs to host and curate such materials, and studied the technological feasibility of the development and operations (Buttenfield, 1998; Fraser, 2001; Zhao, Rotem, & Chen, 1999). With regard to the area of bibliographic information mining, services based on text mining like virtual referencing, citation visualization and citation recommendation were proposed (Hoerber & Khazaei, 2015; Moyo, 2004; Takasu & Ohta, 2015; Wu, Hua, Li, & Pei, 2012). Some other services that holds potential include author profiling (Amini, Ibrahim, Othman, & Selamat, 2014; Koltay & Tancheva, 2010; Shoaib, Daud, & Khiyal, 2015), content enrichment such as in text semantic annotation (Cunningham & Knowles, 2005; Wu, Hua, Li, & Pei, 2012), information filtering (Bishop, 1999; Hanani, Shapira, & Shoal, 2001), knowledge management (Islam & Ikeda, 2014; Kaczmarek, 2006), and what was proposed over a decade ago but gaining momentum in practice only in recent years: digital publishing and the RDL as publisher (Bonn, 2002; Lavendel, 1998; Özek, 1999).

Challenges for the academic library have emerged continuously in the past two decades, during which rapid technological development and adoption have taken place. On the one hand, collaborations among libraries, information technologists and scientists to address the issues of information federation, curation and retrieval

were called for, in the face of a dramatically increasing volume of digital artefacts (Hey & Hey, 2006). On the other hand, the potential for digital libraries to play a part in digital preservation was recognised, but did not attract sufficient attention while the field was focusing on establishing primary infrastructure. Storage, migration, conversion and management strategies are main issues among many that attracted most attention in the early days (Hedstrom, 1997), while preservation was picked up years later in the prevalence of Institutional Repository.

The topic of digital libraries evaluation carries a considerable amount of literature. Usability testing has been used widely for assessing digital library interface design and functionalities (Allen, Bullian, Burke, & Jaworowski, 2001; Jeng, 2005a, 2004, 2005b), Joo and Lee (2011) presented a set of metrics for digital library assessment by conducting a usability study, in which they identified four determining elements: efficiency, effectiveness, satisfaction and learnability. Other methods used include quantitative research such as user survey (Kantor, 1999), outcome-based evaluation (Seadle, 2003), and the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) approach used by Shim and Kantor (1999, 1998) back in the 90's.

User acceptance of digital libraries was systematically studied based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) in which the authors pinpointed "perceived usefulness" and "perceived ease of use" as top determinants (Thong, Hong, & Tam, 2002) for digital library service adoption. Last year, Singh and colleagues (2015) developed a digital library acceptance model with respect to social construct theory, to formulate recommendations for digital libraries to enhance the effectiveness of their service delivery.

2.2.2 The role of librarians in the digital library era

The expansion of academic and research library functions in terms of digital services, such as digital libraries and institutional repositories, has inherently led to further elaboration of the role of librarian. The librarian's role has evolved alongside the shifts in the technological landscape and the functions of the academic library as pointed out by Adams and Blandford (2002): "Web accessible digital libraries are identified as changing the role and working patterns of library staff". For RDLs to be implemented effectively and in a manner users will accept, librarians also have to take on the designer role, leveraging their knowledge of the community they serve. In *Librarians as Publishers* Wittenberg (2004) investigated library publishing activities and put the valuable asset of librarians' information management insights in the centre of scholarly communication in the digital age.

Several prominent trends have emerged under the topic of integrating digital library services in research workflows, for example having librarians shoulder the responsibility of supporting researchers with digital literacy (Bell & Shank, 2007; Choi & Rasmussen, 2006; Cox, Pinfield, & Smith, 2014). In the meantime, studies

recommended and emphasized that both library staff and patrons should improve their digital literacy to efficiently utilize library services enabled by advanced technologies (Crane & Rydberg-Cox, 2000, Kibirige & Depalo, 2001; Olele, Abraham, & Emasealu, 2015). The increasing demand for opening up research data by funding agencies also created downstream demand for digital data management training services from the librarians (Nicholson & Bennett, 2016; Pinfield, Cox, & Smith, 2014; Tenopir, Sandusky, Allard, & Birch, 2014).

2.3 Open Science

Open Science had been gaining support from research organizations and funding bodies in recent years. According to ROARMAP⁵, up until now almost 80 funding agencies have mandated some level of open access to publications and data. The total number of research organizations that adopted open access mandates or formulated open access policy is reaching 800 worldwide.

In the UK, Research Councils UK (RCUK) released a position statement on Open Access in 2005⁶, applying the term to all publicly funded research outputs and mandating the implementation of an OA policy⁷ in 2013, followed by specially allocated grants⁸ to cover OA publishing costs. In a press release published April 22, 2016, the European Commission announced the aim to “open up by default all scientific data produced by future projects under the 77-billion-euro Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, to ensure that the scientific community can reuse the enormous amount of data they generate”. This goal will be enabled by the establishment of the European Open Science Cloud infrastructure.

Before Open Science became a complex umbrella term in recent years, it was used in a vague sense of “making science more accessible to the general public” in the long standing discourse on the lack of effective communication between academia and the wider society (Shargool, 1979). The topic of discussion further extended to the barrier of international scholarly communication between researchers later in the 2000’s (Forero-Pineda & Jaramillo-Salazar, 2002). When consideration was drawn to a broader science policy discussion, the notion of Open Science gained momentum, and triggered wider discussion on the allocation of scientific research resources and the economic performance of knowledge transactions between higher education/ research institutes and the commercial sector (Partha & David, 1994). At the turn of the twenty-first century, discussion on the potential of Open Science was again picked up by the environmental and geosciences community as a powerful approach to addressing the imperative climate change challenges by aggregating and sharing

⁵ <https://roarmap.eprints.org/>

⁶ <http://www.rcuk.ac.uk/documents/documents/2005statement-pdf/>

⁷ <http://www.rcuk.ac.uk/documents/documents/rcukopenaccesspolicy-pdf/>

⁸ <http://www.rcuk.ac.uk/media/news/121108/>

research data via community platforms like PANGAEA⁹. In the face of this potential paradigm change, Ioannidis (2012) complemented the Utopian scientific communication Nosek et al envisioned (2012) with more specific concerns on practicality, and called for further examination from the researcher community. Mukherjee and Stern (2009) on the other hand, proposed a series of scenarios on the outcomes of Open Science and closed science, established mathematical models for each scenario and concluded that the feasibility of Open Science is grounded in the incentives for disclosure and strategic interaction among researchers.

Various definitions of Open Science are found in literature, each emphasizing a different aspect or agenda. An exploratory study done in 2011 with experts in the scholarly communication field about their opinion on some key Open Science topics including reproducibility, credibility, data sharing and open peer-review found a lack of consensus on what the term means (Grubb & Easterbrook, 2011). Without providing a definition of what Open Science is, Fencher and Friesike (2014) identified five interpretations of Open Science with respect to their different emphases, where technological architecture, accessibility of scientific research product, comprehensibility of scientific impact measurement and collaborative research were identified and mapped to their corresponding stakeholder groups.

A model showing the main topics in the Open Science discussion and their interdependencies is presented in *Figure 1* as a summary of the literature. The Openness in Open Science is expressed through rapid development of the conceptual and technical interoperability between infrastructural information systems that is crucial for achieving accessibility and improving discoverability of scholarly contents. Both accessibility and discoverability have come to be considered basic requirements of scientific research output by funders, publishers (Pulverer, 2015), institutions (Vines et al., 2013; Hildreth, 2014) under the Open Science principles. Major topics in the interoperability area include the introduction of Persistent Identifiers (PID) for researchers and research output (Brase, Sens, & Lautenschlage, 2015; Briguglio, Pacquing, Salza, & Guercio, 2015; Dallmeier-Tiessen et al., 2014), universal metadata harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH (Devarakonda, Palanisamy, Green, & Wilson, 2011), and evolving demand for flexibility and versatility of metadata syntax (Auth & von Maur, 2002; Fortuna, Oniga, Padrah, Mohorcic, & Moraru, 2012).

Accessibility to knowledge and knowledge production tools sits in the centre of Open Science. Investigated topics are Open Access publishing of articles and data (Pulverer, 2015), long-term digital preservation (Vines et al., 2013; Hildreth, 2014), and information retrieval techniques coupled with digital literacy improvement

⁹ <https://www.pangaea.de>

programs (Kibirige & Depalo, 2001) to address both human and technical components.

Accessibility together with discoverability, in the meantime, underpin two main drivers of Open Science: scientific integrity that can be ensured by reproducibility (Vitek & Kalibera, 2011) and economy and innovation boosted by reusability (European Commission, 2015). Discussions on reproducibility of science focus on effective documentation of research processes, preservation of physical and virtual research conditions and compliance to open standards. These led to investigation on research data publication and versioning. Open peer-review is brought up as another community-vetting mechanism that encourages early exposure of manuscripts and data used (Morey et al., 2016; Bohannon, 2013). Reusability of science plays a role in incorporating the interested public into the realm of scientific research -- the popularity of Citizen Science and crowdsourcing research projects present a strong argument for this claim (Franzoni & Sauermann, 2014; Hand, 2010; Newman et al., 2012), and laid the cornerstone for open collaboration across disciplines and distance (Bernhard, Bittel, Bettoni, & Mirata, 2015; Jørgensen et al., 2015; Nielsen, 2012).

Upon achieving reproducibility and reusability goals, an integrated, more comprehensive approach to the scholarly excellence assessment method can potentially be formulated, based on the quality and social impact of the research outputs (Alhoori & Furuta, 2014; Pepe & Kurtz, 2012; Tenopir et al., 2015). The CRediT project at CASRAI exemplifies such an effort. The project aims to refine the authorship crediting system by understanding and identifying different contributor roles in research, which can potentially cause profound changes in project and personnel evaluation.

Figure 1. A model organization of Open Science topics.

Open Science inevitably poses challenges for scholarly publishing. Aside from the development of Open Access publishing models on digital platforms, publishers also face new practical questions when it comes to the demand of disaggregating article information and extract “research objects” instead (Bechhofer et al., 2010). To accommodate research objects, Carral and colleagues (2015) looked at an ontology of particle physics data analysis that is essential for capturing experimental results.

2.3.1 Open Access

The first and foremost issue addressed in the Open Science movement is accessibility. In the first formal call for action -- Budapest OA initiative (Chan et al., 2002) -- scholars categorized two strategies to approach OA: Self-archiving, prototype of Green OA, and Open Access Journals, later Gold OA. Shortly after some attempts in OA implementation, McCulloch (2006) presented an overview of OA progress and roadblocks, and identified copyright issues, confusion of terms used and publisher policies as some major barriers for OA adoption. Libraries reacted soon after to contemplate the implication of OA for university libraries (Lor, 2007), and the incorporation of OA journals in library collections (Sweezie et al., 2007). In the following years more investigation was conducted on the implementation opportunities and the caveats of OA, for example the requirement of

Institutional Repositories (Smith, 2008; Lam & Chan, 2007) and university OA publishing services (Bargheer and Schmidt, 2008). In the HEP field, the concept of the Gold OA initiative SCOAP3 was also conceived during this period (Mele, Morrison, D'Agostino, & Dyas-Correia, 2009). In the 2010s, discussion on OA for research data and other educational resources started to gain interest among the higher education and researcher community (Sampson et al., 2012; Giglia & Swan, 2012), and again in HEP, article-data integration was studied as a precursor to the Open Science paradigm shift (Praczyk, Nogueras-Iso, Dallmeier-Tiessen, & Whalley, 2012). Others explored publishing data through comparable publishing channels to article publishing (Andreoli-Versbach & Mueller-Langer, 2014). Discussion on the practicalities of OA is still continuing, but the concept of OA has grown considerably from access to shelves and publications in the early days, to research data today.

2.3.2 The pragmatics

The pragmatics of Open Science refers to research, products and solutions/ services that address the efficiency of scientific communication -- ways to increase accessibility, foster collaboration, facilitate interoperability and assure reproducibility (Fecher & Friesike, 2013).

There are a number of examples of existing effort for enabling wider collaboration/ participation: self-organizing team building platforms for collaborative research (Bernhard, Bittel, Bettoni, & Mirata, 2015); the DCO project of deep carbon science utilizing an open knowledge portal with open data to support new collaboration opportunities (Ma et al., 2015). Wang and colleagues (2015) pointed out the existing need for deeper understanding of contextualized collaborative information behaviours in order to identify useful function design for information retrieval systems.

In recent years efforts have been made to tackle practical challenges that emerged in enabling collaboration, author disambiguation and result dissemination, with interoperability being one of the most prominent and important. Persistent Identifiers (PID) offer to uniquely identify digital objects, thus reliably and permanently interlinking author and research objects (Rueda et al., 2013; Haak, 2014)

One of the primary arguments for pursuing reproducible science on the practical level, including investigating technical solutions for increasing the reproducibility of scientific research outcomes, is based on scientific philosopher Popper's idea of science itself: "Non-reproducible single occurrences are of no significance to science" (Popper, 2005). One defining survey on open data and data sharing provided a comprehensive view on researchers' perceptions of and attitudes to these new concepts and practices, resulting in a list of incentives and barriers emerging from the study (Tenopir et al., 2011). Efforts along the same lines identified determinants

for willingness to share data (Wicherts, Bakker, & Molenaar, 2011; Sayogo & Pardo, 2013). Pioneering efforts were made in mapping out data publishing options and procedures -- data as its own unique output or “data paper” that inherit similar publishing requirements from articles. The outcome of these explorations indicate the necessity of involving the wider stakeholder community including traditional publishers and new innovative publishing platforms alike (Austin et al., 2015). In parallel, working groups also delved into the complex task of data versioning¹⁰, as the importance of data provenance becomes increasingly recognized by open data practitioners (Ram, 2013). Other investigations include the potential of using open peer review to reinforce reproducibility of research (MacLean et al., 2015), such as the possibility of transparent publishing that emphasizes transparent peer-review and open data (Pulverer, 2015).

One of the attempts in changing traditional publishing through the Open Science initiative is to bring the open pre-print repository to the forefront, facilitating in-depth scholarly communication through open peer-review and manuscript versioning on the pre-print repository platform, effectively moving (open) peer-review post “publication” (Tracz & Lawrence, 2016). PeerJ¹¹ and F1000Research¹² are two prominent examples (Ford, 2015).

2.3.3 Infrastructure

RDLs comprise pivotal infrastructure in Open Science (Hey & Hey, 2006). New recommendations and technical solutions for Open-Science practices can either be developed based on RDL functionalities, or designed to be easily integrated into RDL platforms to increase engagement and generate wider impact in the scientific communities.

Scholarly communication infrastructure comprises not only technological facilities, also organizations, standards and other human led efforts that advocate, support and incentivize Open-Science practices (Brown, J. & Cruise, P., 2015). *Table 1* shows examples of these infrastructural units.

Technical Infrastructure	
Metadata standard	Marc21, XML, JSON, JSON-LD
Digital information system (Open source)	Invenio, DSpace, Fedora, EPrint
Universal protocols	OAI-PMH protocol, Shibboleth standard

¹⁰ <https://rd-alliance.org/data-versioning-rda-8th-plenary-bof-meeting>

¹¹ <https://peerj.com/>

¹² <http://f1000research.com/>

Persistent Identifier	ORCID, DOI, handle
Distributed computing	Worldwide LHC Computing Grid, Open Science Grid, European Grid Initiative
Cloud storage	Open Science Cloud
Human Infrastructure	
THOR	Technical and Human infrastructure for Open Research (THOR) project: THOR aims at establishing “seamless integration between articles, data and researchers across the research lifecycle”, by putting together both technical and human component (Brown, J. & Cruise, P., 2015).
FOSTER	Facilitate Open Science training for European Research (FOSTER) project: FOSTER aims to “set in place sustainable mechanisms for EU researchers to FOSTER Open Science in their daily workflow, thus supporting researchers optimizing their research visibility and impact” (Melero, Reme & Grigorov, Ivo, 2016).

Table 1. Examples of infrastructure of scholarly communication.

2.4 High-Energy Physics

HEP seeks to resolve the fundamental question of the origin of our universe. This requires high-level collaboration with theoretical physics and experimental physics jointly addressing core physics questions, often making use of massive collaborative experiments on the large scale laboratories, such as the Large Hadron Collider, that can easily involve hundreds to thousands of researchers (Rolf-Dieter et al., 2008). This unique disciplinary background poses both opportunities and challenges for scholarly communication, especially digital library systems. Fry’s analysis on information needs and practices across academic fields based on Whitley’s mutual dependence theory found that academic fields that require highly interdependent workflows and low “task uncertainty” can more readily co-produce digital resources and better adopt digital communication practices (Fry, 2006). The HEP workflow seems to present an extremely high level of interdependence and low technical task uncertainty.

Just like the data collected from the particle detectors, information exchange in the HEP community is also layered and highly structured due to its unique disciplinary culture and workflow. Experimental physicists who are embedded in large collaborations, physics groups, and research teams, often have little need to

regularly communicate with people outside of their working group. Sometimes communication is even avoided between collaborations to ensure the independence of analyses for result cross-checking -- a crucial step in producing reliable physics analysis results.

2.4.1 Scholarly communication in HEP

Scholarly communication in the HEP community has always been open in nature, and built upon a level of mutual trust that's rarely seen in other nature sciences (Goldschmidt-Clermont De Smaele, 2002; Delfanti, 2016). This is signified by its pre-print culture that was nurtured since the 1960's -- In order to accelerate communication, manuscripts have been shared among the HEP community prior to formal publication for many years, first by mail and more recently via open digital repositories after the invention of the World Wide Web at CERN (Aymar, 2009). A benchmark study of HEP physicist information resources found that more than 90% of HEP community member choose to trust and use community based systems, with an almost negligible percentage of commercial service usage (Gentil-Beccot, Mele, Holtkamp, O'Connell, & Brooks, 2009). These habits strongly motivated information professionals and technologists working in the HEP field to initiate collaborative service-building activities in which librarians, information system architects and scientists work together seamlessly to achieve the highest service quality. Innovations in scholarly communication propelled by the massive demand of this close-knit community are represented by the INSPIRE digital library (former SPIRES database), the arXiv pre-print repository, and the invention of the World Wide Web (Rolf-Dieter et al., 2008). Each of these technologies and the services that followed brought more efficiency and enabled more academic freedom, due to which the HEP communication becomes a rare model that attracted interest from information scientists worldwide.

Prior studies in information seeking behaviour of researchers in different disciplines and at different levels of seniority had shown considerable variation in choice of approach, source-use, and method. While researchers in the humanities and social sciences habitually choose to use citation chaining and content browsing for literature searching (Ellis, 1989), historically, HEP scientists prefer to communicate new results through indexes, and place significant emphasis on the content of abstracts for the purpose of easy navigation (Brown, 1999; Heuer, Holtkamp, & Mele, 2008). There is opportunity for a detailed study of how the HEP research workflow, in addition to the disciplinary environment, shape and impact the information behaviour of the scientists.

2.4.2 Information services in HEP

The "community bookshelf", arXiv¹³ pre-print repository is historically used by physicists to quickly disseminate their results. It forms a digital representation of early paper-based pre-print circulation. It is now so recognized within the community that it is used as the principle "publishing" platform, even a venue to increase researcher visibility (Delfanti, 2016; Pinfield, 2001).

Even though most disciplinary literature is freely accessible through this community repository, the CERN Scientific Information Service still actively seeks to comply with the formal open access publishing route. The Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics (SCOAP3)¹⁴ initiative was started in 2008 as an innovative solution to achieve gold open access to HEP publication: through redirecting subscription funding to OA publishing fees, the initiative aims to form a consortium to make peer-reviewed publication in HEP open to all. Since its start in January 2014, SCOAP3 has supported Open Access publication of more than 10,000 articles by 18,000 authors from 100 countries (Mele et al., 2009).

INSPIRE¹⁵ digital library is a collaborative effort led by 5 HEP institutions around the world that now serves the community as a central information hub under expert curation (Holtkamp, Mele, Simko, & Smith, 2010; Ivanov & Raae, 2010). INSPIRE is the result of the integration of historical HEP database SPIRES and modern open source digital library framework Invenio. Using a hybrid of automatic and manual harvesting methods, INSPIRE ingests disciplinary content comprehensively, and provides a series of value-adding services including reference analysis, citation tracking, author profile aggregation and options for users to contribute information to improve and enrich its content. Recently, the feasibility for RDLs to integrate bibliographic records with research data was explored, and a test implementation is being developed as a collaboration between INSPIRE and HEPData, a service that was built at the Institute for Particle Physics Phenomenology at the University of Durham (Dallmeier-Tiessen & Mele, 2014).

An additional service, CERN Open Data Portal ¹⁶(CODP), was established as a platform for the actual output of CERN physicists' work to be accessible to the general society. The portal also provides reuse possibility by offering authentic data captured by particle detectors on the LHC, as well as data analysis tools that are necessary to reproduce analysis results for both educational and research purposes (Herterich & Dallmeier-Tiessen, 2016; Cowton et al., 2015).

¹³ <http://arxiv.org/>

¹⁴ <https://scoap3.org/>

¹⁵ <https://inspirehep.net/>

¹⁶ <http://opendata.cern.ch/>

CERN Analysis Preservation is an innovative service conceived during the development of CODP, when the lack of data provenance information raised challenges during the process of data consolidation for final release. The service aims at ensuring reproducible science by providing a solution for preservation of digital research objects (data, code, documentation and notes) early in the research process (Chen, et al., 2016).

2.5 Conclusion

This chapter presents a review of literature on the tradition and innovations of communication and information services in the HEP community; development and current state of digital research libraries for research; and the origin, development and ongoing discussions of the Open Science movement. The analysis of the literature has revealed that technological advancement holds great potential for what digital libraries can do with regard to facilitating Open-Science practices. Social and economic drivers are pushing the advancement of Open Science development, on the other hand, engaging the scientific community in adopting corresponding practices is both vital and less well understood.

The research, once completed, will address the so far under-investigated topic of community engagement in novel RDL service(s) in HEP that are offered in line with Open Science recommendations. It will further provide a reference model for fostering community engagement in existing services by understanding the relationship between physicists' workflows and Open-Science practices, suggesting realistic solutions RDLs can offer to address Open-Science practices for physicists, and trialing potential new solutions.

The study will contribute in understanding HEP scientist's workflow and their information seeking and data sharing behaviour, as well as in providing strategy and requirements for community digital library to actively engage users.

3. Methodology

The methodology chapter introduces the research design and investigation methods chosen for the project. The research uses a mixed methods exploratory strategy in the first two phases, followed by a third qualitative testing phase. The preliminary qualitative phase informs the data collection and data interpretation of the subsequent quantitative phase to form a hypothesis. The results from the first 2 phases jointly inform the design of the third phase, which aims to reflect on the validity of the hypothesis proposed and build on the result. In the end, a meta-analysis that incorporates all final results from previous analyses is proposed, to address the main research question and further discussions. The logical workflow is depicted as a diagram in *Figure 2*.

Figure 2. Overall research design for the PhD

3.1 Research strategy and research design

The main research question - How can RDLs support and engage HEP scientists with Open-Science practices or "Open practices"? - contains multiple high level concepts and seeks an integrated answer that addresses different aspects of HEP research activities. For this reason, it is proposed to take a pragmatic approach and break the main research question down into more fundamental components that can be used as building blocks to higher level understandings. Each concept in the main research questions: HEP, RDL and Open Science, provide a distinct perspective for looking at the core subject of user engagement, and each aspect can be applied as a lens to probe at the main question in order to reach a comprehensive response.

Perspectives that will be taken into account are, first of all, the disciplinary one: the environment that shapes current practice, and how it addresses openness. Secondly, the RDL perspective: the elements of RDL that are effectively stimulating interactions from users/ scientists, and whether these elements inherently contribute to "Open practices". Finally, the perspective of the individual scientist: their perceptions on information practices, i.e. activities that are required, or deemed important, worthy of investment in time and energy, etc. Then the study will synthesize information gained from all aspects, and realign the analyses results to formulate a hypothesis on engaging "Open practice" support mechanism development for RDLs. Lastly, the investigation will return to focus on the scientists' perspective, to validate the hypothesis, and generate recommendations that take community feedback into account. The underlying theme throughout the investigation is the question of Openness. The way Openness will be incorporated in each analysis will be explained in detail in the corresponding section in this chapter.

The first phase of the study aims at understanding the HEP culture, research workflows and practices. This knowledge will act as a basis for benchmarking HEP scientists' current practices against "Open practices" and build the understanding of the applicability of Open Science in the disciplinary context. Interviews with scientists are being conducted to investigate these open questions. Through analysis of Open Science applicability to HEP, a list of practices expected from, and potentially adoptable for HEP researchers can be derived.

The result from the qualitative study in the first phase will provide key concepts that will inform the quantitative study in the second phase, which aims to look at how RDLs are supporting HEP scientists currently, and what aspects of RDL services/ functions effectively engage scientists. A quantitative analysis of the user-system interaction log of INSPIRE digital library should reveal features that encourage engagement. Together with the analysis result from the previous stage, this will shed

light on the compatibility between relevant Open-Science practices in HEP and services offered by RDLs that support these practices. A categorization is illustrated in *Figure 3*. Elaboration on the chart can be found in sub-section 3.2.2.

Figure 3. Categories of possible outcome of phase 2

Depending on the results from the study described above, it will then be possible to generate a hypothesis on how RDL can better engage researchers in the third phase, then proceed to investigate and propose concrete next steps according to the scenario(s) identified. Focus group discussions with scientists are planned to find verify these suggestions, and in so, test the validity of the hypothesis.

An integration and interpretation phase is proposed to be implemented by the end of all investigations, with the aim to consolidate all findings and build a holistic understanding of the issues essential to HEP scientists' adoption of Open-Science practices. A conclusion can be drawn from this, and used to guide further RDL development in HEP, and possibly, evaluate its generalisability to other information systems.

The following sub-sections will further elaborate on the method to be implemented for each phase.

3.2 Investigation method

3.2.1 Phase 1: Qualitative strand – interviews

Figure 4. Section from research phase diagram: phase 1

To survey the conventional research practice and the disciplinary environment, semi-structured interviews are proposed to be used as the investigation method. Considering the exploratory/ descriptive nature of this phase, the format of semi-structured interview was chosen because it has the flexibility to encourage the interviewees to express their perceptions and opinions freely, while at the same time providing the mechanism to confine the conversation within the scope of the research topic (Bryman, 2006).

Specifically, the investigation aims to look closely into HEP researchers' information seeking and information sharing practices. As encapsulated in Wilson's information

seeking behaviour model (1981), on the individual researcher level, these practices are likely to be driven by a complex of interrelated beliefs, attitudes and perceptions of the environments, either cultural, economic, or personal. Specifically, pinning down research practice means defining research tasks, how these tasks are approached, using what methods/ tools and how they are used. These elements can be propelled or constrained by one another, or impacted in different ways by forces external to the research cycle, such as the emphasis on communal spirit due to the collaborative nature of the discipline. A descriptive account of these impact factors and their relationship with the practices adopted by the researchers can be deduced from the interviews, to aid our understanding of the HEP context.

To gain ground-level insight of physics research practice requires a heterogeneous purposive sampling of the candidate pool (see section 6 Interview), in order to sufficiently validate the quality of results. Literature research shows no consensus on the number of qualitative interviews one should conduct to guarantee the best result, but considerations that should be taken into account are relatively clear: sample pool size, categorization of sample pool, practical limitations, saturation criteria, etc. (Baker & Edwards, 2012) After synthesizing these factors, a number of 20-25 was decided for the interview research. The execution of the interviews will be described in the interview section.

The outcome of phase one will be a list of research practices, their driving forces and limitations. This result can act as a basis for a triangulation practice that takes into account factors surfaced among the HEP researcher community and principles/recommendations generated by the wider Open Science stakeholder community. This will enable the evaluation of the practices list with respect to their current Openness and potential Openness, thus answering the overarching question of the compatibility of Open Science principles and HEP research practices, and providing a valid scope of quantitative data collection for the following phase.

3.2.2 Phase 2: Quantitative strand – user log analysis

Figure 5. Section from research phase diagram: phase 2

areas of scientific research. Consequently, INSPIRE users and their usage of the platform, in some way, represent the community's collective perception of a "standard" RDL.

The technical infrastructure and service development of INSPIRE is based and maintained at CERN, while the operation and administration tasks are distributed among the 5 partner organizations. The INSPIRE team uses the open source web analytics platform Piwik¹⁷ for usage monitoring and performance gauging. The availability of Piwik data provides a window to look at researcher information needs and information seeking habits from a different angle. The tool captures a wide range of user data that enables a suite of analytics functionalities including event

¹⁷ <https://piwik.org/>

tracking, content tracking, visitor segmentation, visitor profile, etc. To decide the final selection of log data to be harvested and analysed, the result from the previous qualitative phase will be taken into account. This will also ensure the consistency of the investigation and the validity of the qualitative and quantitative phase integration.

Through a consolidation of results from the interviews and the log analysis, it is expected to locate the exact features that attract and retain user attention, and the underused features. This can be accomplished by inspecting clicks on functional features, combined with the motivations behind the engagement and the reasons for advertence by associating these behaviours to research practices and attitudes.

After obtaining qualitative insight of research practices and quantitative evidence for INSPIRE usage, the synthesis can be done in 2 sequential steps: 1) categorize the relationship between the features offered by INSPIRE and research practices, and 2) produce recommendations for each category.

There are four categories for all possible scenarios, when combining the different openness level of the practices and engaging level of the RDL features (see *Figure 3*):

1. "Open practices" that are supported by engaging features
2. "Open practices" that are supported by under-used features
3. Conventional practices that are supported by engaging features
4. Conventional practices that are supported by under-used features

The term "support" here indicates the capability and potential of the RDL feature to facilitate, in a certain aspect, one or a set of research activities. An example for scenario 2 would be usage of data submission form on INSPIRE.

Beside the ones listed above, other possibilities are 1) Conventional practices that are not supported by RDL, or 2) Research practices that cannot be facilitate by RDL. These scenarios fall outside of the research scope, thus only their potential impact on other practices, if any, will be discussed.

Together with one other possible scenario that can be identified from phase 1, i.e. "'Open practices' that are not supported by RDL", general recommendations can be suggested each of the scenarios, to either reinforce the current state (e.g. for scenario 1), or adjust RDL feature to increase engagement (e.g. for scenario 2), or guide researchers to adopt "Open practice" (e.g. for scenario 3). However, how the recommendations will take shape highly depend on the actual result of the analysis, and what research practices or technological features are under inspection.

3.2.3 Phase 3: Testing of hypothesis - focus groups

Figure 6. Section from research phase diagram: phase 3

To find out the HEP community's attitude for the proposed changes in RDL platform and their potential willingness for adapting to new practice, focus groups are planned to facilitate discussions among HEP researchers based at CERN, the same candidate pool that was used in the first phase of study. Focus groups are a powerful tool for gathering users' opinions and comments on early concepts of new functions and features, and they will constitute a preliminary viability test for the recommendation proposals generated in the previous mixed-methods investigation; in another words, they will determine whether the improvements proposed are likely to induce the changes predicted.

The design of the focus groups will greatly depend on the results gained from the previous stage. In principle, the qualitative and quantitative data analyses results should be able to provide a good understanding of the general picture and set a solid basis for generating relatively specific plans for improvement, e.g. a plan for better supporting each potential "Open practice". The four categories illustrated in *Figure 3* could each trigger a unique follow up discussion. The goal of the follow up discussions directly affects how the focus groups will be designed, arranged and moderated. But the ultimate aim of the focus groups is to assess the viability and desirability of the recommendation proposals with the user community, before they can be designed and implemented.

3.2.4 Phase 4: Integration and interpretation

The integration and interpretation phase is placed at the end of the research project as a space for consolidation and reflection of the data collected, the analyses conducted and conclusions drawn in each phase, with respect to the original research questions posed at the beginning of the project. It is expected to use this phase to evaluate the appropriateness and effectiveness of the research design, the method and the actual execution by discussing how adequately the investigations answered the main research questions, to what level, and what next steps will be necessary to take in order to further the discussion.

On the other hand, space is also dedicated here to investigate the generalisability of the conclusions regarding: 1) what Openness means with respect to distinct disciplinary environments, and 2) the RDL's role in engaging scientists in "Open practices", in the hope of providing reference for other Open Science service providers.

This phase will consist of content analysis of previous results and possibly feedback from the community, as interim results are made public during the course of the project.

4. Research plan/ Time scale

Time scale for the overarching project is presented in Gantt chart, it should be noted that the plan shown here is from the completion of this confirmation review report, which is subject to revision and resubmission within 6 months after the primary review. The report has undergone major re-construction to incorporate reviewers' feedback, including narrowing down the project scope and adjustments in research methodology. These changes affect the projected time scale for research, also they have redefined the relationship between the investigation process and the INSPIRE development team roadmap. In theory, the log data analysis is closely related to the upcoming INSPIRE upgrade, which will affect both the frontend – user interface and user experience – and backend of the digital library, thus cause fluctuation in user behaviour data. This will be solved by coordination with the INSPIRE development team and further understanding of the Piwik capability (e.g. historical raw user log data export), to determine the data collection schedule.

Figure 7. Research timeline in Gantt chart.

5. Ethics review

5.1 Research procedure that requires ethics consideration

To obtain insights of HEP scientists' daily work, specifically 1) their information needs and interaction with information system in an highly granular level, 2) their perception for existing information services etc., it is decided to leverage the advantage of basing my study at CERN, to conduct one on one semi-structured interviews with scientists who are currently working on site. Interviews requires contact with human subjects, which raises ethical concerns.

5.2 Ethical issues and precautions

The main ethical issues that needs careful consideration for the interviews are post-interview privacy and anonymity of data. Personal safety is minimal, since the study targets adult scientists and located conveniently within their usual work perimeter, indoor, mostly during working hour. On the other hand, information sought for in the interview potentially contain sensitive subjects and personal information that needs access control and anonymization before any kind of public release. This can be achieved by storing raw data in private online directory provided by the university and CERN, and encrypt with passwords to eliminate unsolicited access from outside of the research team (comprised of researcher and supervisors). To ensure data anonymity, any and all raw data will not appear on any article or report that is prepared for publication purpose without eliminating identifiable personal information.

The privacy assurance measurements were explicitly mentioned in the interviewee consent form, and emphasized in the beginning or during interview to carry the message across, and minimize disturbance perceived by interviewees from audio recording.

Ethics approval for the interview was acquired by the University ethics reviewers on February 2nd, 2016, see appendix for full application and approval letter.

6. Interview

A qualitative data collection and preliminary data analysis procedure was planned and carried out during late February and early March 2016. 11 interviews with HEP scientists were conducted at CERN to provide a detailed view on HEP research workflow, information needs and research output, information handling and perceptions about Open-Science practices. The aim of conducting the interviews is to understand HEP scientist's relationship with Open Science and the information tools they use, thus provide ground to address further questions. Up until the point of this confirmation review, the interview is only partially completed, the pause is intended to leave some space for adjusting and narrowing down the scope of certain questions, after deepened understanding gained from previous interviews.

6.1 Setup

Basing at CERN made setting up the interviews relatively easy comparing to regular situation which start with finding reliable access to the community. In the setup period several steps were carried out and the following section is organized in accordance: sampling, data collection and preparation, and preliminary data analysis process and results.

6.1.1 Sampling

Among the 15,000 members at CERN, number of research physicist takes up approximately 2/3 of the total count ("CERN Annual Personnel Statistics", 2014), consisting both theoretical physicists and experimental physicists, although due to the nature of CERN -- a laboratory, only 1% of the research physicists reside in the "theory corridor" at CERN, which is not representative of the HEP community. Considering the digital library service the study focuses on serves the entire HEP community, it does not make sense to use probability sampling for the proposed qualitative study.

A mix of purposive and snowball sampling is being used for the study, taking into account the potential difference in workflow and digital library usage of researchers of different fields (experimental/ theoretical); potential difference in workflow and digital library usage of researchers of different senioritis; potential difference in practice of researchers in different physics collaboration; the main user group of INSPIRE; and the availability of invitees. As the result of these considerations, it is decided to separate physicists in to experimentalist and theorist, then further categorize each group by rankings: PhD students, Postdoctoral researchers and senior researchers, resulting in 6 categories. After establishing the rough guideline of candidate sampling, batches of names can be pulled from several sources: query

scientists who are "active" and affiliate to CERN on HEPNames of INSPIRE digital library; query CERN personnel directory ("CERN Phonebook"), Theory department web page of official CERN website where all theorists and their availability ("who's here when", information available to CERN personnel) are listed. Upon a consolidated long list of potential candidates, individual candidate was shortlisted on a recommendation basis. Due to the personnel structure and varied availability of researcher based on different seniority -- junior researchers (PhD students and Postdoctoral researchers) tend to be more readily available than senior researchers (staff researchers and faculty members) -- the percentage of each category was kept around 40% - 40% - 20%.

	PhD student	Postdoctoral researcher	Professor	Total
Experimentalist	3	3	1	7
Theorist	2	1	1	4
Total	5	4	2	11

Table 2: Interviewee distribution in the first round of interviews.

6.1.2 Interview schedule development

To prepare the interviews, an interview schedule was developed using Google Spreadsheet, in which included interview questions, candidate pool and interview appointment schedules. The interview questions went through a number of iterations with help from supervisors, colleagues and physicist friends. The goal of conducting interviews with physicists is to identify motivations and barriers for scientists to adopt Open-Science practices into their workflow (Paepcke, 1996), to approach this, three topics that will help attaining the research goal were selected:

1. Current workflow: To understand the research lifecycle, work components, procedures (and their determinants), etc. of particle physicists, similarity and differences in workflow among physicists of different seniority.
2. Information needs: To understand at which point external information are needed to carry on with research, what level of communication is carried out, in what format, medium, for what purpose.
3. Information practices: To get insight knowledge of what information sources, services and tools are frequently used and trusted by HEP scientists, their

attitude and opinion on the usefulness and efficiency of them; How do scientists use the services and tools, what functionalities and features are heavily used or desired, etc. (Thong, Hong, & Tam, 2002).

Following these guidelines, 21 questions were formulated to build up the body of the interview content (see appendix for full list of interview questions), excluding supplemental questions used to clarify main questions, and follow up questions emerged from the flow of conversation (due to the semi-structured nature of the interview).

As stated previously, the sampling process is designed to be on a recommendation basis (snowball sampling), thus by the end of each interview invitation to further participants the interviewee see fit was explicitly mentioned. This approach combined with the enthusiasm of the HEP community in supporting community research resulted in an unexpected outcome -- the response rate for the invitation to theorists exceeded 100%. This was due to one of the interviewee sent my interview invitation email to the theory department secretary, who in turn sent it as an open invitation to the department mailing list, which solicited nearly 10 response of interest, at which point I have only personally sent out 5 invitation emails.

6.2 Data collection and preparation

Preparation tasks for carrying out interviews included preparing research related information for invitees, composing and sending invitation emails (meanwhile get in touch with potential contacts upon introduction by supervisor), set up pre-interview meeting when required/ necessary, or deciding meeting time and place with email exchanges.

Meeting rooms can be booked in advance without charge on CERN site, usually the interviews are scheduled at around 16-18h during the week, in meeting rooms located in a central building, to minimize disturbance and hassle for interviewees, and also the rooms are more available during these slots.

6.2.1 Approach

Developing the information sheet is required by the university ethics application process, which is highly useful in the invitation process. The information sheet was used to introduce the research aim and subjective to potential interviewees, with specific information on what the interview will be about, what is the format of the interview, how long it will last and how the data will be recorded, analysed and used. A consent form is attached to the second page of the information sheet, with space for signature of approval from both the interviewees and the researcher. The document is sent along with the invitation email, but signature for consent is only asked for at the interview meeting.

6.2.2 Data capturing

The interviews were conducted in private meeting rooms, recorded, in audio, with an iPhone. The audio capturing performance of iPhone was tested in advance to ensure quality recording, and available storage was checked to ensure data could be captured in full, without disruption.

Transcripts were generated from the recordings in the following weeks of the interview, using open source web application Otranscribe¹⁸. The 11 hours of recording resulted in approximately 75 thousand words transcript, which are stored in encrypted directory on CERNbox (cloud-based storage service provided by CERN).

6.2.3 Data analysis

The data analysis process is still on-going at the submission of this report. Following the thematic qualitative data analysis method posed by Bazeley (Bazeley, 2013), the transcripts were printed, read, imported to NVivo for topical and interpretative coding. Part of the transcript are manually annotated and coded on paper, later these notes will be transported to NVivo for easy interpretation and analysis. Figure 1 showed planned data analysis process.

Figure 8. Interview analysis flowchart (source: *Qualitative Data Analysis*, Bazeley, 2013)

Transcripts are thoroughly read, repetitively and comparatively, for meaningful annotation, then it carries on into the coding process -- annotation and coding are

¹⁸ <http://otranscribe.com/>

mutually complementary procedure, some annotation directly translate into code nodes, some codes provide new perspective to data and leave space for new annotation. After enough loops in the annotation-code process, codes are generated exhaustively, they can be organized and analysed. Interpretation and ideas can be generated from all steps mentioned, then ideas and code interpretations can be summarized into themes, which directly feed into the final conclusion.

7. Research training

7.1 Training Needs Analysis

See appendix.

7.2 Research ethics

Research ethics is required module for doctoral students at the University of Sheffield, as a remote location student I didn't have the chance to attend the lectures and workshop under this module in person, yet I have duly followed the materials made available on MOLE system before taking any action on research planning and data collection.

7.3 Qualitative research method

Qualitative method module provided an overview for a number of basic methods commonly used qualitative research projects, each presented with specific examples and step by step analysis. These lectures together with the recommended readings -- especially the Baker and Edwards report on how many qualitative interviews is enough (Baker & Edwards, 2012) helped immensely during the process of preparing for the interviews with physicists.

8. Reflection and conclusion

In the first year of the PhD was to a degree chaotic, to say the least, but according to well appreciated communication with fellow PhD students and graduates -- which is extra valuable for a remote-location student -- it is common to struggle a little as one experience the dynamic nature of scientific research and make peace with it. I had a hard time striking a balance between ambition and reality in different aspects of research and personal life, but by the end of the first year, I am pleased and confident to say that some order is established, which should more steadily carry the research further towards fruition.

In addition to the standard inauguration steps into a PhD project: devising research plan, conducting literature review, deciding methodology for research, and obtaining research training via online modules provided by the university, I have also, thanks to the advantageous position of basing at CERN, took a step forward and collected the first batch of field data from a set of interviews conducted with CERN particle physicists. The progress is satisfying, and I look forward to carry on with the research -- in the immediate future: continue the interviews to reach a deeper understanding of physicist workflow, perception on Open-Science practices and digital library services, and wrap it up as an independent mini project that can be disseminated to the community.

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